

RESO

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WPD half-hourly operational electricity distribution network data. Methodology for creating usable data and recommendations for future data sharing

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WPD half-hourly operational electricity
distribution network data

Methodology for creating usable data and
recommendations for future data sharing

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This report has been prepared for the West Midlands Regional Energy System Operator (RESO) project under the Innovate UK Smart Local Energy Systems Prospering From the Energy Revolution detailed design programme.

Glossary

BEIS	Department of Business Energy and Industrial Strategy
WPD	Western Power Distribution
RESO	West Midlands Regional Energy System Operator
DSStn	Distribution Substation

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the experience of the University of Birmingham's, Energy Informatics Group in conjunction with David Phillips of Wattify Limited in collating, comparing and cleaning network asset data and half-hourly operational timeseries data for the Regional Energy Systems Operator (RESO) project area. The main underlying data has been provided via Western Power Distribution's (WPD's) participation as a supporting partner in the RESO project through resources from WPD's Innovation Team and the WPD assignment of David Phillips of *Wattify Limited*. Additional supporting data was sourced directly through WPD's website either publicly or after registration and login. The RESO project is indebted to the Innovation Team at WPD for making the network asset and half-hourly timeseries data available to be evaluated and utilised within the project.

The network asset description and substation timeseries data files have been uploaded to the <https://es-dc.org> website, which requires registration and login. Permission to view and download the data files have only been made available to RESO project members with a direct interest in the half-hourly data, and the data is subject to restrictions on its use. The data is therefore subject to the highest level of security and restrictive use within the RESO project. In practice, the raw data has been evaluated, cleaned and aggregated by Dr Grant Wilson, Dr Joe Day and David Phillips.

The two main recommendations from working with WPD data are based on understanding that adding unambiguous asset numbers and expressing datetime data in UTC using an ISO 8601 compatible format would reduce the uncertainty surrounding timeseries data, and decrease the time taken to make the data useable for further analysis.

Recommendation 1: All network infrastructure assets should have an unambiguous unique asset number

Recommendation 2: All datetimes should be expressed in UTC using an ISO 8601 compatible format

2 BACKGROUND

In 2019 the UK was the first developed country to pass a net zero emissions target into law. Being net-zero by 2050 underpins the UK's commitment to the UNFCCC COP 21 2015 Paris Agreement to keep global warming under 2°C. However, the cumulative amount of emissions are the driver of climate change rather than the net-zero target itself *i.e.* it is the amount of CO₂ emissions released on the pathway to net-zero which is the important factor. Nonetheless, the net-zero target by 2050 provides a singular and defined target after which the UK will no longer be adding to an increase in Green House Gas emissions.

The Regional Energy System Operator (RESO) project is a detailed design project funded by Innovate UK from January 2020 to December 2022 with a focus on the decarbonisation of Coventry local authority area. Through the RESO project, a cleaner, lower cost energy system for Coventry and the West Midlands region that maximises economic opportunities in clean growth and future mobility, will be designed. Its aim is to help deliver local policy objectives towards net-zero emissions in 2050. Targets for Coventry will be set within the wider context of climate ambition at a national level.

An aim of the RESO project's detailed design methodology for Coventry is to demonstrate its relevance to the wider region by having an approach for other local authority areas that can potentially be replicated.

Within the overall RESO project context of creating a detailed energy system design, the Energy Informatics Group at the University of Birmingham provides input to the project on data foundations with a particular focus on energy data.

A critical element of any energy systems analysis is to have access to detailed data on the energy system assets within the area. In addition, where available, operational data associated with these assets can provide a deeper understanding of any untapped benefits the network might potentially support by smarter local operation. For example, a better understanding of where the local electrical network has capacity could help inform a detailed design of the system in 2032. The half-hourly timeseries data from WPD is therefore felt to be an important element of a more detailed understanding of the scale and variability of electrical flows within Coventry.

Operational data must be suitable to any organisation that creates them, otherwise the expectation is that internal processes and internal users would feedback for the data to be more appropriate to their needs. The challenge that organisations have when sharing data outside of their historical channels, is that other 'formats' might be considered more desirable. This report presents lessons and learning on the preparation of raw data shared by WPD so that it could then

be further cleaned and analysed. This report also presents some data recommendations that could improve the format of similar shared data in future.

2.1 Context for Coventry

The city of Coventry is an administrative centre and metropolitan borough in England with an area of 98.64 km². According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS) estimates, the population of Coventry in mid-2018 was about 366,800¹ with the Gross Value Add per capita standing at £21,382² (ONS Dec. 2015) £24,890³ (ONS 2017). With an area of 98.64 km², Coventry local authority is 58% built on, 17% green urban, 25% farmland and <1% attributed to natural area. This includes 138,460 domestic buildings⁴. According to the 2013 figures, there is 15.9% fuel poverty compared to the national average of 10.4%.

Area boundary: The RESO project boundary includes 201 LSOAs. This is shown in Figure 1 and consists of the 195 Coventry Local Authority Area (LAA) LSOAs, and six additional LSOAs Warwick 005G, Rugby (004D, 001C), Nuneaton & Bedworth (015C, 015D, 015E). Electricity distribution network boundaries do not neatly match to Local Authority or LSOA boundaries, and therefore some *guard band* asset data that is not physically within the area is also included.

1

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/bulletins/annualmidyearpopulationestimates/mid2019>

2 https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/file/20837/coventrys_economic_output_-_gross_value_added_per_head

3

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossvalueaddedgva/bulletins/regionalgrossvalueaddedbalanceduk/1998to2017#interactive-map-gross-value-added-gva-per-head-for-nuts3-local-areas-1998-to-2017>

4 <https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dataset/dwelling-ages-and-prices/resource/dwelling-age-group-counts-lsoa>

FIGURE 1 - MAP OF THE 201 LSOAs OF INTEREST FOR THE RESO AREA. THE 195 COVENTRY LOCAL AUTHORITY LSOAs ARE IN GREEN AND THE 6 LSOAs OUTSIDE THE LOCAL AUTHORITY BOUNDARY ARE IN YELLOW

Electricity networks (substations, cabling and related equipment) in the area are largely owned and operated by WPD with a number of independent DNOs (iDNO) assets and private connections. There are 6 WPD Bulk Supply Points (BSPs) - 5 regular 132/33 kV and a sixth BSP connection supplying only the Coventry South 11 kV primary). The BSPs supply 25 WPD Primary High Voltage (HV) substations in turn supplying 1,190 Low Voltage (LV; 11 kV/400V or 6.6 kV/400V) substations, but some of these do not exclusively supply the Coventry City Council area. WPD owns 25 HV substations supplying power to 11/6.6 kV (for LV substations) within RESO’s area plus 3 supplying from just outside with a further 4 primary connections / substations owned privately by e.g. JLR plc or iDNOs, a total of 31 supplied at Jan 2020.

Coventry HV networks have two notable characteristics: around 40% of them operate at 6.6 kV (legacy and not operable at 11 kV) and is constrained, notably by generation headroom at some primary and/or fault levels. Coventry connects to the national transmission grid at two grid supply point (GSPs): Berkswell and Coventry 132kV, both grid constrained⁵.

5 see East Midlands: <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/distributed-generation-ehv-constraint-maps>

FIGURE 2 - EHV DIAGRAM FOR COVENTRY AREA, SOURCE EMU
[HTTPS://DATAPORTAL2.WESTERNPOWER.CO.UK/MAP WPD®](https://dataportal2.westernpower.co.uk/map/wpd)

3 WPD TIMESERIES DATA

3.1 Background to Network Monitoring from WPD

The growth in low carbon technologies and distributed generation means network demand, peak flows and power quality are becoming less predictable. The assets on WPD’s network are monitored to drive cost effective operations as a DNO (and an emerging DSO) and to help actively manage performance and defer or avoid reinforcement. Whilst this monitoring data is not specifically designed for smart local energy systems, WPD has recognised it can help partners with common goals, such as providing a better understanding and therefore potentially enabling future distribution networks to meet growing demands for low carbon technologies. As a project partner in the RESO project, WPD shared detailed data under licence to the project and has welcomed feedback on the data process as the experience of the RESO project may have wider application.

WPD publishes a range of guidance⁶ to assist projects and partners in understanding network monitoring. This includes case studies to help use of measured power (MVA, MW and MVAR) and how to make valid analyses of these different categories of data.

Monitoring systems typically report half-hourly average measurements on WPD assets, covering a range of parameters such as power, current, temperature and tap position. The monitoring infrastructure to create the data is located where WPD needs visibility for effective systems operation – these are usually installed down to primary substation site level.

The main dataset provided by WPD were half-hourly timeseries data totalling circa 200 Mb in size. The timeframe covered by the data was nearly three years' worth of this half-hourly data from July 2017 to February 2020. Interestingly, this covers data for nearly 3 heating seasons (including the Beast from the East event on the first of March 2018). It does not cover the impacts of Covid-19 social distancing measures which came into effect at the end of March 2020. The timeseries data were mostly from HV primary substations monitoring and included transformer data as well as feeder data at the HV/MV level (i.e. not LV feeders).

To allow this data to be made available and analysed, the RESO project entered into a formal partnership with WPD giving access to data under specific terms and conditions for its use which protects WPD as the data owner. Details are set out in the licence agreement on the es-dc data sharing platform that accompanies the raw, parsed and cleaned data.

The RESO project was uniquely supported to receive large sets of WPD monitoring data for evaluation via WPD's interim extraction tool, with assistance from the WPD Innovation Team. The ad-hoc manual approach used to enable this type of data sharing is suitable only for innovation purposes and has no operational support service, hence the RESO approach is unlikely to work at scale across larger projects/regions.

WPD has supported more repeatable extracts with data naming readily matched between datasets (see Appendix 3 and work completed to study CIM/INM in the South West), but at the time of the initial RESO data request the systems for East Midlands did not yet support this.

⁶ <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/smarter-networks/network-strategy/dsof>

The wider RESO project therefore did not have direct access to an API for data downloads, rather the data was available for bulk data download via a HISTAN⁷ export file by David Phillips of Wattify. This was subsequently uploaded and shared under licence conditions on the es-dc platform as a series of 12 separate files (for the initial bulk data set). This manual non-API process could in principle be repeated periodically so the underlying files could be refreshed by re-querying to get more recent data in a time series. More repeatable approaches are currently in development at WPD and this interim approach allowed RESO to access single manual exports of innovation data. However, this approach, as explored in the feedback in this document is not a suitable process for ongoing use. RESO was advised to check for completeness of data and were felt to have substantial up-to-date coverage of Coventry with a time-lag of about 1 month from real-time.

4 RAW DATA FILES DESCRIPTION

The raw data shared by WPD through the es-dc platform were available in yearly data downloads (2017, 2018, 2019, 2020), and each year was further split into a number of csv files into fractions of the year. Only the first csv file of each year contained the header information for the columns, whereas the other files for that year only contained rows of data; there were no column headings in these files.

A python script was created to recombine the 12 separate data files back into a single pandas dataframe. The script is shown in Appendix 4.

The number of columns in each csv differed between years due to additional data columns becoming available; this was thought to be as monitoring data came online during a year. The number of columns could also differ between csvs within the same year, as the headers for each csv part of a year were only contained in the initial csv of each year. Thus, if monitoring started part way through a year, its header would appear in the initial year csv header row, but the values would not appear until the monitoring started. If this happened to be after in the 3rd or 4th csv dataset for the year, then the column of data in the 2nd or 2nd and 3rd csv datasets would simply be a column with no data that the python read_csv import function could import, in effect a completely blank column. This caused the python script to throw an error as there was a mismatch in the number of columns between subsequent csv files for a particular year being imported. This type of problem might be able to be minimised if the ad-hoc manually downloaded dataset were to be downloaded by asset, rather than split along years *i.e.* downloading all the data for a primary substation over all time periods, rather than downloading the data for all substations for a defined time period. This initial

⁷ HISTAN is a WPD internal platform

challenge of combining data back together that would have originally been in a database exemplifies the risks and extra work with manual downloads. The desire to have data in a form that could subsequently be cleaned and analysed with the minimum of parsing, all point to the benefit of setting up an API for this type of data enquiry in future.

4.1 Datetime format

The data contains dates from 2017-07-17 to 2020-02-13

The raw format of the date column e.g. 'Monday 07/07/2017' for the start date to 'Thursday 13/02/2020' for the end date combines the string for the day of the week (with a sentence case capital letter) with the date value in UK based excel format (back slash between day/month/year). It has the date and the month numbers zero padded to two digits and the year as a four-digit number

Surprisingly for timeseries data, there is no actual time data, instead, there is a column of integer values (titled 'Serial Date/Time') that is similar to an index, as the values increment by a value of 1 for each row. The format for the integer value is not padded with prefixed zeros, and is simply the integer, i.e. the first value in the column is '1' rather than '00001', this means the column cannot be sorted using simple text commands, but would need to be understood by the code to be numerical in order to sort the digits as intended.

The initial parsing of the 12 data files to join back into a single large file created a csv with 766 columns of data with 45216 rows. The 'Day/Date' column was parsed into a date with a format of yyyy-mm-dd e.g. 2017-07-17. The number of rows for each day was then checked, to see if there were differences between the short day in March and long day in October due to clock changes for daylight saving during British Summer Time. For expected values for each half-hour of localtime, there would be 46 values in a short day (last Sunday in March) and 50 values in a long day (last Sunday in October).

Exploratory Data Analysis showed that each and every day in the raw data had 48 values (rows) associated with it, as such, there were no short or long days. Typically, this would point towards the time values being in UTC rather than local time; as UTC has no clock changes applied it has 48 half-hourly values for each and every day. However, on further inspection of the data for days in March with clock changes (the last Sunday in March, 2018-03-25 and 2019-03-31) it was found that the 3rd and 4th rows in these days had values that were all set to a value of '0.003'. This suggested that the value '0.003' was being used in the data as a 'null value' flag to differentiate from blank values that would simply be blank values. This 'null value' data for the 3rd and 4th rows in a clock forward day (01:00 and 01:30) means that the dataset is not in UTC. This would then typically point to the data being in localtime, meaning that the October long day would have 50 data points.

Given that there were 48 values (rows) in every day, including the day ending British Summer time (clock backward day last Sunday in October) this indicated that the dataset was not strictly in local time either. In local time with half-hourly values, there should be two repeat values that increase the standard count of 48 values to 50.

The dataset was therefore felt to be what could be termed a ‘pseudo’ local time, where all but 4 values were in local time. The values that were not in local time were the repeat values in October (where one set of values did exist, but the repeat values did not) and the values that should not exist at all in local time in March, but do appear in the dataset. A likely explanation of this ‘pseudo’ form in the data can be when an original local time with a gap in values in March (two missing values) and repeat values in October is parsed to remove repeat values. Further steps might include interpolation to provide the datetime index for the missing values in March (which do not exist in local time), and then filling the blanks with the values of ‘0.003’ in this case. This has been experienced before with other operational datasets analysed by the Energy Informatics Group and is therefore not an uncommon occurrence. However, without an obvious trail of blank, or interpolated, or other data suggesting some manipulation for the March values it can be tricky to know which datetime format is presented. Typically, data will be shown in either UTC, localtime or pseudo localtime. If there is an obvious feature in time series energy data that shifts forward by an hour in British Summer Time, this provides additional evidence that the datetime format is UTC.

The risk of attributing the incorrect datetime format to the data (UTC and pseudo localtime both have 48 half-hourly values for each and every day) can be mitigated by having a standard datetime value as UTC. It is straightforward in python (and thought to be the same in other coding packages) to create localtime values from UTC values, but it can be much more involved to recreate UTC values from pseudo local time.

For further analysis and for comparison between different energy vectors and weather variables, it is necessary to create a UTC datetime format from the data. A UTC datetime format reduces uncertainty surrounding the datetime values and makes timeseries analysis considerably easier between different energy supplies and demand. This is one of the underpinning recommendations of the Energy Informatics Group for any energy system data, that it has a UTC datetime data. Details of the raw data files is shown in Table 1

TABLE 1 – VALUES IN WPD TIMESERIES RAW DATA. CLOCK CHANGE DETAIL.

Year	From: Date and Serial	To: Date and Serial	March clock change (local time jumps forward at	October clock change (local time jumps backward at

	Date/Time columns	Date/Time columns	2pm on last Sunday)	2pm on last Sunday)
2017 (3 csv files)	Monday 17/07/2017 1	Sunday 31/12/2017 8064	n/a	There are no repeat rows, 48 rows in the last Sunday
2018 (4 csv files)	Monday 01/01/2018 1	Monday 31/12/2018 17520	2018-03-25 The Serial Date/Time column continues to increment by 1. However, all data values set to 0.003	There are no repeat rows, 48 rows in the last Sunday
2019 (4 csv files)	Tuesday 01/01/2019 1	Tuesday 31/12/2019 17520	2019-03-31 The Serial Date/Time column continues to increment by 1. However, all data values set to 0.003	There are no repeat rows, 48 rows in the last Sunday
2020 (1 csv file)	Wednesday 01/01/2020 1	Thursday 13/02/2020 2112	n/a	n/a

The data is therefore felt to represent local time but with the double values in October having simply been dropped to keep the number of data points in a standard year at 17520. This means that all datapoints in the year would be correct for localtime, other than the repeat values in October that have been removed, and the values in March that should simply not exist in local time at all.

To recreate datetime values with a UTC time series the following steps were taken:

- 1) delete the 3rd and 4th rows of the clock forward days that contained missing values that simply cannot exist in local time (local time in clock forward days jumps from 00:59 to 02:00, there are no local time values between 01:00 and 01:59)
- 2) add two additional rows after the third and fourth row in the clock forward days, and provide data for the blank values for these by interpolating between the previous value and next non-blank value. There were now 48 values for a standard day, 46 for a short day and 50 for a long day.
- 3) the starting datetime was set to 2017-07-16 23:00 for the UTC value, as the original 'localtime' value was 2017-07-17 00:00 +01:00. As this is within British Summer Time this equates to the 2017-07-16 23:00 UTC value
- 4) the ending datetime was set to 2020-02-13 23:30 – the same as the original end date and period – as this was not in British Summer Time, it is the same as UTC
- 5) a datetime index was created from these starting and ending datetime values with a frequency of 30 minutes. This was then made timezone 'aware' to be UTC.
- 6) Having made the datetime index timezone aware, it was trivial to create a local time column so this was also included. This still had 17520 values in a standard year, but had one short day with 46 values each March and one long day each October. This is the format for localtime rather than a pseudo localtime.

4.2 Naming of monitored data categories

The first 5 or 6 rows of the first csv for each year (termed part 1) contained the data for the header information for that years' worth of data. The first row always contained the feeder name text, and the row titled 'Site Name' contained the name of the site; this could be a primary substation, its upstream 33kV connection point, a Bulk Supply Point or a 132 kV Grid Supply Point. In the 2020 part1, there was an additional row titled 'Analogue Type' which was not present in the other years. The data values are highlighted in blue in the following snapshots, the format of the Day/Date column can be seen, with the starting value for the Serial Date/Time column always being 1.

The header names highlighted in red can be seen to contain useful information on the site, the feeder, and the type of data being monitored. In many cases these also contain units such as MVA, MW, MVA_r and kV. However, there is no asset number data associated with the headers, either for the site, or the feeder.

The Site Name row contains the name of the site (in most cases the primary). These names are mostly similar to, but not always the same as the SubstationName data from the WPD Network Capacity Map Data or the RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1_PRIMARYS_11032020.csv file that had been uploaded to the es-dc website for this purpose. Therefore, the names of site from the timeseries data (the sitenames) opened up a source of potential error, as there could be more than one textual description or representation of an asset.

It was therefore necessary to undertake a manual cross-checking exercise to match the Site Name row data in the timeseries with the WPD Network Capacity Map Data or the RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1_PRIMARYS_11032020.csv file to determine the 6-digit number of the asset. Not all the Site Names were contained within the RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1_PRIMARYS_11032020.csv file (not all sites of monitoring are Primary), therefore the WPD Network Capacity Map was used to fill in the gaps. Nonetheless, even with the two datasets to manually match the SubstationName and the Substation Number, there were two sites that did not match to any 6-digit number. These were Coventry North 132kV and Whitley 132kV – these are 132 kV feeder sites that have monitoring sites associated with them.

Once a 6-digit number had been manually checked and matched against a sitename, this was used to prepend a parsed column name, so that any further analysis would unambiguously tie a particular column of data to an asset number e.g. a primary substation.

Using the site names alone was not a reliable way to match Primary or Substation names across the different data files, as there were special cases for example at a primary level, where the same site name “Courthouse Green” is used in monitoring data for two Primary substations – one at 11 kV and one at 6.6 kV. There were other difficult to match cases, usually at a Bulk Supply Point with two or more site voltage levels, where the text in the names matched but with the addition of a numerical value e.g. “Coventry West 132” and “Coventry West 33”, reflecting that feeders are present at two voltage levels at the same BSP.

Day/Date	Serial Date/Time	AnstyAerospace Research CentreYellow current
Raw Data Condition		Stuck value 0 longest run 3073 points Integer vals
Site Name		Ansty
Export Control Flag		
Monday 17/07/2017	1	0

Day/Date	Serial Date/Time	AnstyAerospace Research CentreYellow current
Raw Data Condition		Stuck value 0 longest run 2066 points Integer vals
Site Name		Ansty
Export Control Flag		
Monday 01/01/2018	1	73.25

Day/Date	Serial Date/Time	AnstyAerospace Research CentreYellow current
Raw Data Condition		Stuck value 0 longest run 2389 points Integer vals
Site Name		Ansty
Export Control Flag		
Tuesday 01/01/2019	1	0

Day/Date	Serial Date/Time	AnstyAerospace Research CentreYellow current
Analogue Type		11 FEEDER
Raw Data Condition		Data all Zeros Integer vals
Site Name		Ansty
Export Control Flag		
Wednesday 01/01/2020	1	0

In order to future proof the data for analysis by WPD or the RESO project, it was decided to rename the asset column headers to include both the substation number and the Substation Name that agreed with the RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1_PRIMARYS_11032020.csv and the WPD Network Capacity Map Data (Appendix 1 has details of the match across between asset names and numbers in these data sources)

A structured inventory management approach was found to be useful in building comprehensive lists of substations with the associated data needed by other aspects of the RESO project (other than half-hourly monitoring analysis). One such inventory is the list of WPD distribution (LV) substations (1,100 DSSStns) which are themselves fed from a usually unique and stable 11/6.6. kV feeder. Capturing this Feeder ID with each DSSStn where available and using the associated Primary name for each inventoried DSSStn was a useful pairing of data that helped to add back feeder IDs to approximately 250 of the 11/6.6. kV feeder monitored time series (“Yellow Current” monitored ones that feed WPD DSSStns from a site of a Primary). The 6-digit primary name and a 4-digit feeder number (from the breaker) were combined to provide a numerical code for the 11/6.6. kV feeders. The joining character was a backslash / which could potentially cause problems with

further data parsing, but was chosen as this emulated WPD’s feeder format on the EMU mapping on <https://dataportal2.westernpower.co.uk/Map>

Where further data is present associated with a primary the last three digits are letters indicating the function or component such as T=Transformer; P=Active Power. Additionally, there was a number to represent the component e.g. T1 (transformer number 1 of typically 2 at a Primary).

The python script to carry out the parsing steps presented in this chapter is shown in Appendix 4. This code recombines the 12 csv files into one dataset, creates a UTC and localtime column, adds asset numbers to column headers, calculates a check step power column from the sum of current feeders, adds flag columns to help with further manual data cleansing and saves all of this into individual csv files per asset e.g. per HV primary substation. These parsed individual files were uploaded to the <https://es-dc.org>.

At this point, the data was ready to be cleaned.

If the raw timeseries data had a datetime format in UTC and was able to be downloaded via an API, then the steps in this chapter (and the associated code) could mostly be avoided, and analysis would be accelerated to the cross checking the naming of assets and then data cleaning and further analysis.

5 WPD ASSET DATA NAMES AND NUMBERS

WPD has published a Network Capacity Map on the website <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/network-capacity-map/>

FIGURE 3 – INITIAL WPD WEBPAGE

On Figure 3 Click on the button 'No, thank you, just show me the map'

FIGURE 4 - ACCEPT TERMS AND CONDITIONS

On Figure 4 click the 'I accept the terms and conditions *' checkbox and the 'OK' button

Error! Reference source not found. should be visible:

FIGURE 5

Rather than limit the data download by using the drop-down menus on the left of Figure 5, the data button on the upper left is toggled and brings up Figure 6

FIGURE 6 - DATA VIEW

Click the 'Export Data' button to download the 1.5 Mb file of all the 1382 assets (as of 2020-06-20). This data file details 67 columns of data, not all of which have a value for each data point.

The 67 data columns contained within the download are detailed in Appendix 5

The Network Capacity Map data provided a further dataset to be used to cross check the Substation Name and a Substation Number against the text name descriptions for the asset data uploaded to <https://es-dc.org>. This Primary cross-checked data is detailed in Appendix 1.

However, a limitation of the Network Capacity Map data set is the lack of a version number for future referencing. The data could be timestamped in terms of its download datetime, but when the data changes (annually) this is not specifically defined in a version number. This is a common problem to many public facing online datasets. There are also a number of limitations pointed out by David Phillips such as the classification of assets in the manner that the RESO project would define them.

Although the network capacity map data had a rich source of data, it was only used for cross checking asset names and numbers. It was unclear how robust the additional categories of data were for the assets e.g. headroom, short circuit currents, fault level headroom.

If there was a robust and uniform asset naming strategy across all datasets, then the steps of cross checking to name the assets could become a trivial matter.

6 WPD TIME SERIES DATA RECOMMENDATIONS:

Adding unique asset numbers and expressing datetime data in UTC using an ISO 8601 compatible format would reduce the uncertainty surrounding timeseries data, and decrease the time taken to make the data useable for further analysis.

Recommendation 1: All network infrastructure assets should have an unambiguous unique asset number

Recommendation 2: All datetimes should be expressed in UTC using an ISO 8601 compatible format

6.1 Asset and time-series data

The data was made available through the process detailed in Appendix 5

The format of the raw data from WPD was not usable by the RESO project in its raw form. A significant amount of time was devoted by the Energy Informatics Group and David Phillips to accomplish three basic tasks:

- 1) Combining the 12 separate raw data files back into a single data file
- 2) Providing a UTC datetime for each row in ISO 8601 compatible datetime format
- 3) Matching the header data with other WPD asset data e.g. the asset number for primary substations, and the feeder or breaker number for feeders from the primary substation

These steps were required for WPD's data simply to get it to a point where cleaning and checking steps could then take place. Cleaning and checking steps are typically required of all operational data, but the basic steps of parsing data into a form that is then able to be cleaned are not. This is an area that WPD should consider addressing in order to make the data more useable to external stakeholders; these steps could also potentially make the data more useable for WPD's internal purposes too.

The first two tasks listed above were undertaken by a python script (Appendix 4), the third task was undertaken in two stages i) a python script to match the sitenames names in the timeseries data asset headers to the WPD Network Capacity Map Data, and ii) a further python script to match with a file giving feeder (breaker) numbers. This was a csv that used the asset header from the timeseries data itself (prepared from task 1) and a unique ID surrogate created by David Phillips and manually coded against the asset header text; this code was typically the primary substation name and feeder (breaker) number.

There are a number of sources of potential error with this method, and it not particularly scalable to the level of DSSn due to the number of these in the area (>1100).

In any future timeseries data download from WPD, an asset data file is therefore necessary to reduce the need for manual crosschecking. This would also help to automate a consistent naming schema across WPD assets, by providing a unique asset number for each asset e.g. GSP, BSP, Primary, 11/6.6 kV Feeder, Distributed substation, LV Feeder etc. and a consistent naming policy across the different types of data. For example, all tap position data could have an alphanumeric code that can be added to the asset number.

All datetime data should be provided in UTC datetime rather than localtime. The existing practice of providing '0.003' values for the clock change forward in March and dropping the repeat data on the clock change back in October should be stopped and replaced with a process that expresses all datetime values in UTC using an ISO 8601 compatible format.

UTC is more robust for calculations and analysis and it can be changed to localtime for visualisations and discussions when local time is a more appropriate expression of datetime than UTC. In terms of futureproofing the interoperability across the wider energy sector between different energy vectors, and with weather data, UTC should be a de-facto requirement for sharing timeseries data.

The use of unambiguous unique asset numbers would allow additional data to be more easily shared in different csvs. For example, an 11 kV feeder could have much of the data that is available in the Network Capacity Map (headroom, fault limits, locations etc.) provided after checking for the most recent changes. Also, the asset numbers of LV substations associated with each feeder (under typical operation of normally closed points) also allows further analysis to be undertaken; csvs of these would be therefore be useful. In essence, knowing the asset numbers of HV substations, the assets connected above and below these, and the asset numbers of the connections between the assets provides a more complete picture of the network that timeseries data can be allocated against. Having all of these based on unambiguous unique asset reference codes, and having the data shared via csvs (or similar) means that data can be cross checked within computer scripts. This reduces the need for manual copy/pasting or text checking and therefore reduces the risk of errors. UTC and unambiguous asset references provides the basis for more machine-readable data.

This would then leave the effort of data preparation able to be focussed on the cleaning of data, rather than the basic manipulation of data even before cleaning can take place.

6.2 Additional lessons from working with WPD data

- i) The WPD documentation on the Distribution System Operability Frameworks (DSOF) topics⁸ titled “Network Monitoring and Visibility” and “Data and Forecasting” is helpful.

In addition to the asset number and UTC steps to increase the usability of the data, having additional knowledge of the typical underlying data itself would be useful in the metadata alongside the datasets. To assist partners in analysing timeseries, DNOs may be able to share more knowledge on the features of different of monitored data that would help with the identification and cleaning of errors. This could usefully cover several common events:

- a. Common observed time-series features due to typical network reconfigurations
 - b. Monitor channel pre-processing behaviour – e.g. “nonsense” sensor conditions;
 - c. Any data acquisition conventions used *such as*: what does the value 0.003 itself denote in the data, what does the value 0.003 when added to a number (other than zero) denote. What does the number 0 denote? What would a completely blank value denote?
- ii) Feeder Names can be long and contain compound data which can be harder to work with. Each feeder’s time-series should be extracted with their corresponding feeder ID number wherever available “at-source”. (There is a convention for most HV Feeders to be assigned a CB number). Helpful if WPD could provide name/ID mapping tables where at-source labelling is not possible. With this, it would much easier to work with 11/6.6. kV Feeder data – associating them with their respective primary/number and other data with matching Feeder IDs such as local LV substations.
- iii) Share data in a single file is more helpful than across several files. Splitting/Batching of data files opens up opportunities for errors, and may not be a trivial matter to simply re-join the files back together. If the HISTAN system has limitations in this regard in terms of the amount of data that can be downloaded at one time, then it should be investigated to split across assets, rather than splitting across years, as this might make additional data parsing easier.

⁸ <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/smarter-networks/network-strategy/dsof>

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- iv) **Missing higher levels.** Good coverage of Primary was obtained. Later it was found higher levels of the network are also useful. For 33 kV (BSP) level more site names are needed to extract; At 132 kV, 2 GSP Feeder measurements were found to be missing (not in the Sweep list - same root cause). These should be flagged at the outset to avoid delay/future runs.
- v) To assist at BSP/GSP, it would be very helpful to have a comprehensive gazette of all channels – names and IDs if possible – This would help with pre-selection of all feeders and measures needed at all site-levels.
- vi) Ideally, monitoring data would be available from DNOs via an API to allow up to date data to be accessed by those parties with a secure API login. A significant step prior to the availability of the underlying monitored data would be access to an up to date list of the asset names and IDs (perhaps via an API too). If not full data, make all the header data available via API. This singular asset database would then form the basis of naming and ID numbers that would be used for further analysis.

<Input Name>	<Substation>	<Notes>	<Substn ID>
Ansty	Ansty 33 11kv S Stn		930061
Copsewood	Copsewood 33 11kv S Stn		930044
Courtaulds	Courtaulds 33/6.6kv		930026
Courthouse Green	Courthouse Green 33/11kv S Stn		930033
	Courthouse Green 33/6.6kv S Stn	<i>?Also extract using same PC</i>	930035
Coventry Arena	Coventry Arena 33/11kv		930083
Coventry North 11kV	Coventry North 11kv S Stn		930046
Coventry North 132kV	=>	<i>N 132kV interconnector?</i>	
Coventry North 33kV	=>	<i>BSP site?</i>	
Coventry South 11kV	Coventry South 11kv S Stn		690014/930032
Coventry South 132kV	Coventry South 11kv S Stn	<i>S interconnector?</i>	
Coventry South 33kV	=>	<i>BSP?</i>	
Coventry West 6.6kV	Coventry West 6.6kv S Stn		930025
Cox Street	Cox Street 33 6.6kv S Stn		930031
Dillotford Avenue	Dillotford Ave 33 11kv S Stn		930042
Dunlop	Dunlop 33/6.6kv		930039
Gulson Road	Gulson Road 33 6.6kv S Stn		930043
Hawkesmill Lane	Hawkesmill Lane 33/6.6kv		930028
Holbrook Lane	Holbrook Lane 33/6.6kv		930038
Holyhead Road	Holyhead Road 33 11kv S Stn		930037
Jaguar Browns Lane	Jaguar Browns Lane 33/11kv		930029
JLR Whitley	=>		
Kenilworth	Kenilworth 33/11kv		930050
Lawford	Lawford 33 11kv S Stn		930055
London Road	London Road 33 6.6kv S Stn		930027
Newdigate	Newdigate 33/11kv		930079
Ryton	Ryton 33/11kv		930049
Sandy Lane	Sandy Lane 33 6.6kv S Stn		930040
Spon Street	Spon Street 33/6.6kv		930041
Torrington Avenue	Torrington Avenue 33/11kv		930030
University of Warwick	University Of Warwick 33/11kv		930034
Walsgrave	Walsgrave 33 11kv S Stn		930047
Whitley 11kV	Whitley 11kv S Stn		930045
Whitley 132kV	=>	<i>POF ref. for 132 site at Whitley?</i>	
Whitley 33kV	=>	<i>POF for BSP?</i>	

FIGURE 5. INITIAL SWEEP LIST (BASED ON PRIMARY - MISSING 5 ASSETS LATER FOUND USEFUL)

7 LESSONS FOR OTHER PROJECTS SEEKING TO UTILISE DNO ASSET TIMESERIES MONITORING DATA

Some wider lessons are listed here for consideration by other projects that wish to benefit from access to DNO asset timeseries monitoring data. Although the WPD data for RESO was focussed at the HV level, the lessons would seem to be appropriate for the LV level too.

When engaging with a DNO to discuss access to monitoring data, projects are strongly recommended to:

- have a **direct project relationship/partnership** with the relevant DNO/Innovation Team or DNO data team for exchange of needs, interests, to request data and provide feedback
- have **experience within the project of an expert power partner** with a strong engineering background in power measurement and experience with smart local energy systems. If this experience is not already available within a project, it should be secured with additional resources and support
- discuss with the DNO how they will resource access to the monitoring data data/access and agree sharing terms **well before Project Start**. It may help if the DNO is recognised as an innovation project partner and Non-Disclosure Agreements can take significantly longer than anticipated to agree
- agree a **defined geographic boundary(s)** enclosing the system of interest (typically the geographical areas of interest supplied by the electricity network). This area of interest should include an **area guard band** (*extending the beyond a tight geographical boundary*) or suitable way of checking for cross-boundary flows⁹
- work with the DNO to create a single definitive reference list for the assets contained within the area of interest e.g. Primary, BSP and GSP substations for the project BSP/GSP areas. A full index of monitored sites in the area should be determined by discussion with DNO, and the DNO's ID / naming conventions should be used. For projects analysing data at distribution (LV) substation level: in addition to the HV substation number (e.g. 930392) ensure that each substation's feeder-ID (e.g. 0001) is also captured. The creation of an unambiguous asset register that covers all assets is a critically

⁹ the wider area beyond the above boundary should be considered so that HV/LV and their parent substations and feeders supplying power across the boundary can be included. In rare cases outer sites above primary may be needed. For most urban areas with rural boundaries this may not contribute significantly to catchment of data.

important foundation to build additional data analytics, reduce manual steps and overall improve certainty and interoperability with other analysis.

- **agree the scope of data** available for monitoring by discussions with the DNO *i.e.* using the unambiguous asset register to agree the assets and also the time window for the data (when the data should begin and end)

At this stage, a DNO and a project should have narrowed the data ask down to a range of assets (with unambiguous asset references), and a timeseries of interest *i.e.* the **scope of data** available for monitoring should have been agreed. Within this scope, the data ask could be further narrowed in terms of the categories of monitoring that would be useful, *e.g.* having current and power flows, but forgoing certain data such as temperature of transformers. Experience from the RESO project is that the additional data from these non-energy flow categories is not a computational burden, so a suggestion would be to accept these as part of a data ask as it may help to answer queries that may be thought of further into the project.

In addition, the RESO project also found the following to be of benefit in terms of building knowledge across the project:

- having an overview of the levels of area networks at 132 kV, 33 kV and 11 kV and topology at a geographical level *i.e.* in relation to a typical map of the area;
- **having all notable features** of DNO networks in the area, including any atypical supply points *e.g.* Primary capacity-add from levels other than the typical 33/11 kV

From a project perspective, as can be seen from the data processes undertaken for the RESO project presented within this document the following should be borne in mind by projects seeking to leverage DNO timeseries data:

- **expect to need more than one data extract** and expect to have to reformat the data into one that is more relevant to answer project goals. Allow a significant amount (weeks to months) of project time for reformatting and cleaning. If ultimately this is not needed (due to the format and quality of data already being suitable for project needs) then the project resource could easily be focussed on other analysis.
- **Plan ahead how you will use different monitoring data types** - expect to receive data types as diverse as current, voltage, multiple power dimensions, temperature pertaining to various assets types: 11 kV/33 kV /132 kV Feeders; Transformers; Tap Changers;
 - RESO initially determined that Primary was of greatest interest (transformer power(s) and HV Feeder current)
 - Subsequently, wider areas and higher levels also appear useful

- Projects should be aware that **few local areas or their networks are complete**, they develop and grow. At some point therefore in the lifetime of a multi-year project additional data streams are likely to become available. Therefore, data sets and indeed the unambiguous asset register may show renaming related to upgrades on the network e.g. a feeder that has originally been described as "Future..." will have an updated text description when commissioned into service. However, the unique asset number should be likely to stay the same (again, a benefit of the unique asset registry).

8 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

WPD for sharing the data with the project and being open to and commenting/reviewing the feedback contained within this document and the process to analyse the time series data.

The Energy Systems Catapult for providing the data sharing platform to allow the data to be securely shared between project partners

The funding for this research is from Innovate UK through the Detailed designs of Smart, Local Energy Systems¹⁰

¹⁰ <https://apply-for-innovation-funding.service.gov.uk/competition/350/overview>

APPENDIX 1 – CROSS CHECKED ASSET NAMES AND NUMBERS

Cross checked data from WPD Capacity Map asset data uploaded to <https://es-dc.org> (RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1_PRIMARYS_11032020.csv)

Site name text from the half-hourly timeseries data manually downloaded from HISTAN and shared through the es-dc platform	SubstationName from RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1 PRIMARYS_11032020.csv and WPD Network Capacity Map download	Substation Number from RESO_WPD_CSV_01_v1 PRIMARYS_11032020.csv and WPD Network Capacity Map download
Ansty	Ansty 33 11kv S Stn	930061
Copsewood	Copsewood 33 11kv S Stn	930044
Courtaulds	Courtaulds 33/6.6kv	930026
		930035
Courthouse Green	Courthouse Green 33/6 6kv S Stn	Missing from this cross check is a separate Primary called Courthouse Green 11kV 930033 - unique in Coventry as it shares a common site at 33kV with the 6.6 kV 930035. As a result, there is only one site match for both in Monitoring even though both are in the .csv list above. FOR FUTURE REF: Preferably the 11kV feeders at Courthouse need to be allocated to a pseudo-site name for e.g. "Courthouse 11kV", as it's a different voltage network (If left together, any analysis of feeder powers will be incorrect if both types are summed equally)
Coventry Arena	Coventry Arena 33/11kv	930083
Coventry North 11kV	Coventry North 11kv S Stn	930046
Coventry North 132kV	Coventry North 132kV	NOTE: This is not a primary – it does not add capacity at 11/6.6 kV (the definition of Primary) and so should not be in a list of Primarys. (It is the 132 kV site of a BSP and might still be needed in a list of monitoring sites)
Coventry North 33kV	Coventry North 33kv S Stn	930009
Coventry South 11kV	Coventry South 11kv S Stn	930032
Coventry South 132kV	Coventry South 132/33/11kv	690014
Coventry South 33kV	Coventry South 33kv S Stn	930012
Coventry West 6.6kV	Coventry West 6 6kv S Stn	930025
Cox Street	Cox Street 33 6 6kv S Stn	930031
Dillotford Avenue	Dillotford Ave 33 11kv S Stn	930042

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Dunlop	Dunlop 33/6.6kv	930039
Gulson Road	Gulson Road 33 6 6kv S Stn	930043
Hawkesmill Lane	Hawkesmill Lane 33/6.6kv	930028
Holbrook Lane	Holbrook Lane 33/6.6kv	930038
Holyhead Road	Holyhead Road 33 11kv S Stn	930037
Jaguar Browns Lane	Jaguar Browns Lane 33/11kv	930029
JLR Whitley	Jlr Whitley	939482
Kenilworth	Kenilworth 33/11kv	930050
Lawford	Lawford 33 11kv S Stn	930055
London Road	London Road 33 6 6kv S Stn	930027
Newdigate	Newdigate 33/11kv	930079
Ryton	Ryton 33/11kv	930049
Sandy Lane	Sandy Lane 33 6 6kv S Stn	930040
Spon Street	Spon Street 33/6.6kv	930041
Torrington Avenue	Torrington Avenue 33 11kv S Stn	930030
University of Warwick	University Of Warwick 33/11kv	930034
Walsgrave	Walsgrave 33 11kv S Stn	930047
Whitley 11kV	Whitley 11kv S Stn	930045
Whitley 132kV	Whitley 132kV	NOTE: This is not a primary – it does not add capacity at 11/6.6 kV (the definition of Primary) and so should not be in a list of Primarys. (It is the 132 kV site of a BSP and might still be needed in a full list of monitoring sites)
Whitley 33kV	Whitley 33kv S Stn	930008

APPENDIX 2 - CONTEXT OF MONITORING DATA WITHIN THE WPD DATA IMPROVEMENT ROADMAP

To date, Monitoring data has been used within WPD largely for specialised and internal network operator functions and tends to be deeply integrated and customised for each mission critical system. Sharing for innovation and exploitation has been encouraged and supported by the WPD innovation team but has required manual query tools. These tend to be purpose-built and not designed for timely or API driven data extracts.

This is happening at a time and in a context where WPD has recognised a need to invest in and improve network data. WPD is currently adopting an Integrated Network Model (INM) approach and creating instances of a standardised common information model that will facilitate greater integration and data exchange among each region's systems. To achieve this, many kinds of data and datasets from multiple systems are being catalogued and described in repeatable and clearly described data formats. Time series data has been identified as an area that needs attention since the practicalities of real time measurement can make it especially challenging to build consistent relationships between data in different systems. This points to the requirement for all network operators to shift to a de-facto standard of having all datetime values being expressed in UTC using an ISO 8601 standard format.

This ongoing development has been trialled in the South West region with innovation results shown below and outputs published to WPD partners. As this programme progresses to harmonise systems in other WPD regions up to 2023, time series data for the East Midlands will be more usable and up to date.

In the interim, other routes have been supported and accessed as described in the main text of this report.

Information Network Model (INM) Common Information Model (CIM) - see: <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/innovation/projects/common-information-model>

Currently active WPD Innovation Project(s) centred on data & related principles:

Name	Contact / Link	Overview
POD Presumed Open Data.	WPD Innovation Team https://www.westernpower.co.uk/innovation/projects/presumed-open-data-pod	Data should be easy to find and accompanied by the information needed to understand their content. Reducing barriers to access data will attract innovators who can create operational efficiencies, develop new business models and define new value propositions.

Completed innovation projects include:

- WPD Time Series Data Quality TSDQ NIA project
- WPD INM/CIM - NIA Innovation project

APPENDIX 3 – RESO SHARED TAXONOMY – ATTEMPT TO APPLY COMMON INFORMATION MODEL APPROACHES

8.1 Taxonomy relationships for Smart Local Energy Systems

RESO found the following data relationships to be helpful – for understanding the mapping between Voltage Levels, Equipment and RESO substation lists.

Voltage Level	Physical Asset (conventional name)	RESO Substation datasets	Example of Asset specific WPD Time Series
Voltage	Owner/Name(s) Type description Notes	Cov/RESO dataset/Notes/Link to dataset	/Units Monitoring channel Tag - Example
275 kV	TSO/Transmission system site GSP substation Grid supply point Grid Supply Points are maintained by TSO sites contain swll (upstream site of the GSP - at 275 kV in RE=> transformers stra Supergrid transformers down to Subtransr (no DNO sub)	WattNAV - 2 sites noted	Berkswell 275/132kv Monitoring channel Tag - Example
132 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site site at GSP (downstream site of the GSP - at 132 kV a (no DNO sub)		SGT1 Berkswell 132kV/SGT1
132 kV	DSO/Subtransmission feeder (EHV) feeders connect Normally pairs operated in parallel (no DNO sub)		Berkswell 132kV Berkswell 132kV...
132 kV	DSO/Subtransmission BSP substation Bulk supply point Normally 2-4 transformers site at BSP this is the upstream site of a BSP =>	RESO_WPD_CSV https://data.es.catapult.co.uk/RESO/RESO-Substations-for-W-Mids-RESO-Project/	Coventry West 33kV 5 Str [Time series does not refer to substations - instead refer to WPD Primary Substations for W Mids RESO Proj]
132 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site GT1 / GT2.. grid transformer (pairs are fed from a single GSP) (no DNO sub)	WattNAV - Selected Rites layer	Coventry West 132kV Coventry West 132kV...
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site site at BSP this is the downstream site of the BSP (no DNO sub)		GT3 Coventry West 33kV Coventry West 33kV...
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission busbar joins transformer (busbar monitoring expected to be of lim (no DNO sub)		33kV Bus Section Coventry West 33kV/33kV Bus Section
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission feeder mostly pairs join part meshed (some are fed from 2 BSPs) =>	WattNAV - Selected Rites layer	Coventry Central 33kV/Courthouse Green 1Power M
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission Primary substatk Primary per BS Normally 2 Transformers; a few private cl. RESO_WPD_CSV	WPD Primary Substations for W Mids RESO Proj	Coventry West 132kV... [Time series does not refer to substations]
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site site at Primary this is the upstream site of a Primary sub: (no DNO sub)		[Time series does not refer to substations]
33 kV	DSO/Subtransmission T1 / T1 & T2.. transformer pairs of transformers normally parallel or (no DNO sub)		T1 / measured units Ansty T1 Power Mva
11 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site site at Primary this is the downstream site of the Primar=>	WattNAV Primary list	
11 kV	DSO/Subtransmission site site at Primarý p this is the downstream site of a Primary a=>	WattNAV Primary list	
11 or 6.6kV	DSO/Subtransmission busbar joins transformer (busbar monitoring expected to be of lim (no DNO sub)		Coventry Arena 11 Kv Bus Section Yellow Current B
11 kV	DSO/Subtransmission feeder "10 per Primary Normally radial; some can be fed from en=>	WattNAV 11kV feeders	Coventry Arena Fast Food Yellow Current Feeder
6.6 kV	DSO/Subtransmission feeder "10 per Primary Normally radial; some can be fed from en=>	WattNAV 6.6kV feeders	
11 kV	DSO/Subtransmission Distribution Sub: "10 per feeder (t DSStns can be owned by IDNOs or private=>	WattNAV Local substations are in list of each Feeder	
6.6 kV	DSO/Subtransmission Distribution Sub: "10 per feeder (t DSStns can be owned by IDNOs or private=>	WattNAV Local substations are in list of each Feeder	

8.2 Attempt alignment with Common Information Model (CIM)

RESO noted the direction of travel of WPD common information model inspection work (empirical from South West INM/CIM project outputs).

The structure for the RESO area time series data attempted to align with this previous work, using a sample WPD Class list, drawn from the South West CIM Export 5.0

Voltage Level	Physical Asset (conventional name)	RESO Substation datasets	Example of Asset specific WPD Time Series	Nearest cim:Class	WPD Ref (Item)	Anatomy of Monitoring names (use of Class/ sub-class names/values in data series n
Voltage	Owner/Name(s) Type description Notes	Cov/RESO dataset/Notes/Link to dataset	/Units Monitoring channel Tag - Example			
275 kV	GSP substation site	WattNAV - 2 sites noted	Berkswell 275/132kv	cim:Substation	"Substation"	"Site Name" - header for each time series include this query-field value
132 kV	site		SGT1 Berkswell 132kV/SGT1	cim:PowerTransformer	Transforme cim:PowerTransformer	
132 kV	feeder (EHV)		Berkswell 132kV Berkswell 132kV...	cim:VoltageLevel	"Site Name" cim:Substation [cim:VoltageLevel]	
132 kV	BSP substation	https://data.es.catapult.co.uk/RESO/RESO-Substations-for-W-Mids-RESO-Project/	Coventry West-Coventry Berkswell 132kVCoventry West-Coventry South 2Po	cim:ACLineSegment	"Site Name" cim:VoltageLevel [cim:ACLineSegment]	
132 kV	site	WattNAV - Selected Rites layer	Coventry West 33kV 5 Str [Time series does not refer to substations - instead refer to WPD Primary Substations for W Mids RESO Proj]	cim:Substation	(cim:Substation)	
132 kV	GT1 / GT2..		Coventry West 132kV Coventry West 132kV...	cim:VoltageLevel	"Site Name" cim:Substation [cim:VoltageLevel]	
33 kV	site		Coventry West 33kV Coventry West 33kV...	cim:VoltageLevel	"Site Name" matches cim:VoltageLevel	
33 kV	busbar		33kV Bus Section Coventry West 33kV/33kV Bus Section	cim:BusbarSection	(monitoring cim:VoltageLevel [cim:BusbarSection])	
33 kV	feeder	WattNAV - Selected Rites layer	Coventry Central 33kV/Courthouse Green 1Power M	cim:ACLineSegment	"Site Name" cim:VoltageLevel [cim:ACLineSegment]	
33 kV	Primary substatk	WPD Primary Substations for W Mids RESO Proj	Coventry West 132kV... [Time series does not refer to substations]	cim:Substation	(cim:Substation)	
33 kV	site		T1 / measured units Ansty T1 Power Mva	cim:VoltageLevel	"Site Name" matches cim:VoltageLevel	
11 kV	site	WattNAV Primary list		cim:PowerTransformer	cim:PowerTransformer	
6.6 kV	site	WattNAV Primary list		cim:VoltageLevel	"Site Name" matches cim:VoltageLevel	
11 or 6.6kV	busbar		Coventry Arena 11 Kv Bus Section Yellow Current B	cim:BusbarSection	(monitoring cim:Substation [cim:VoltageLevel] "e.g. Bus Section" "Yellow Current" "Bus"	
11 kV	feeder	WattNAV 11kV feeders	Coventry Arena Fast Food Yellow Current Feeder	cim:ACLineSegment	"Site Name" cim:Substation [cim:ACLineSegment] "Yellow Current" "Feeder"	
6.6 kV	feeder	WattNAV 6.6kV feeders		cim:ACLineSegment	"Site Name" cim:Substation [cim:ACLineSegment] "Yellow Current" "Feeder"	
11 kV	Distribution Sub:	WattNAV Local substations are in list of each Feeder		cim:Substation	(cim:Substation)	
6.6 kV	Distribution Sub:	WattNAV Local substations are in list of each Feeder		cim:Substation	(cim:Substation)	

No time series datetime descriptor or standard has been found within the INM user guide that could assist with standardising monitoring timestamp parsing issues encountered by RESO

IEC 61850 is an international standard that defines a protocol for monitoring at substations. This has a timestamp descriptor – and this would be able to be expressed in UTC.

If the Common Information System helps DNOs to categorise their assets in a consistent way, then a similar basis for consistency is required for the timeseries

data associated with these assets. This should be expressed in UTC in an ISO 8601 format to be consistent. Having UTC timestamp data also provides the benefit of being future proof and allowing easier interoperability with other energy network vectors (heat and natural gas) and with weather data.

Future work aligned with WPD INM

INM has the potential to be extended to support external use cases by making data more consistent and delivering datasets in a repeatable and well-described format. However, it is clear from the below that INM configuration requires a role of Data Steward with substantial insight, experience and direct access to existing WPD systems and working with INM will normally be beyond the scope of 3rd Party projects.

We therefore anticipate any future stakeholders such as RESO having a strong reliance on good working partnerships with WPD with clear expectations of a limited number of common use cases, providing access resulting datasets within service levels that are acceptable to the DNO who is resourcing the use cases.

The following extract explaining the purpose and illustrating what is involved in an INM processing run is taken from v0.6 of the INM Configuration Manual.

The v0.6 Manual is largely silent on the question of DateTime formats or their correct interpretation for time series measurement but does refer to Conversion of dates. A similar function for time would require attention to the issues and suggestions made above regarding UTC normalisation of local time data.

APPENDIX 4 – PYTHON PARSING CODE

```

import os.path
import re
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import datetime as dt
import glob
import time
import math

start_time = time.time()
downloaddate = dt.datetime.now().strftime("%Y-%m-%d")
ClockForwardMarch = ['2018-03-25', '2019-03-31']
ClockBackwardOctober = ['2017-10-29', '2018-10-28', '2019-10-27']

# folders
home_folder = os.getenv('HOME')
folderpath = f'{home_folder}/OneDrive - University of
Birmingham/RESO/RESO_UoB_share/WPD_confidential_data/'
# FolderConfidentialData =
f'{folderpath}primary_substation_timeseries/primary_monitoring_Walsgrave/'
FolderConfidentialData = f'{folderpath}es-dc_2020-05-06/'
output_for_checking = f'{folderpath}parsed_for_checking/'
primarycodes_folder = f'{home_folder}/OneDrive - University of
Birmingham/RESO/RESO_UoB_share/RESO_QGIS/' \

f'RESO_public_data_for_QGIS/from_data_es_catapult/from_WPD_DP/asset_locations_parsed/'
os.chdir(folderpath)
NetworkCapMap = pd.read_csv('WPD Network Capacity Map 2020-06-20-09-14-33-937.csv',
skiprows=0, header=0, encoding='Utf-8', dtype=str)

# this chooses files in a folder where the filenames contain a particular string
os.chdir(FolderConfidentialData)
csvlist = glob.glob('*.*.csv')

# def creates ordered list of filenames of the year's csv files
# 3 in 2017, 4 in 2018, 4 in 2019, 1 in 2020
def parseyears(yyear):
    matches = []
    for partnum in range(1,5):
        r = re.compile(f'.*{yyear}_part{partnum}.csv')
        if list(filter(r.match, csvlist)) != []:
            temp = (list(filter(r.match, csvlist)))
            matches.append(temp)
    return matches

# ordered lists of filenames for each year
match2017 = parseyears(2017)
match2018 = parseyears(2018)
match2019 = parseyears(2019)
match2020 = parseyears(2020)

# def that takes the ordered list and runs through these to join them together
# a few challenges to be overcome: mainly the csv files can have different numbers of
# columns if the csv has blank data on the right. The csvs only have a header in the csv
# titled
# part1 in each year - all the others have no header (which means they will be read.csv with a
# reduced number of columns if there are blank columns
# also, each csv can have multiple blank rows at the bottom that need dropped
def csvjoin(yyear):
    df = pd.DataFrame()
    matchyear = f'match{yyear}'
    for i, filename in enumerate(eval(matchyear)):
        # if statement loads the part1 which has the header data and presumed sets the

```

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```

# width for the concatenated df
# dropna axis=0 drops the blank rows
if i == 0:
    print(f'{i}+{filename[0]}')
    df = pd.read_csv(filename[0], skiprows=0, header=0, encoding='Utf-8', dtype=str)
    df.dropna(axis=0, how='all', inplace=True)
    dfwidth = df.shape[1]
# for the remaining parts -
if i in [1, 2, 3]:
    print(f'{i}+{filename[0]}')
    temp = pd.read_csv(filename[0], skiprows=0, header=None, encoding='Utf-8',
dtype=str)
    tempwidth = temp.shape[1]
    blankdf = pd.DataFrame(index=range(temp.shape[0]), columns=range(dfwidth-
tempwidth))
    temp = pd.concat([temp, blankdf], axis=1, ignore_index=True)
    temp.columns = df.columns
    temp.dropna(axis=0, how='all', inplace=True)
    df = df.append(temp, ignore_index=True)
return df

df2017 = csvjoin(2017)
df2018 = csvjoin(2018)
df2019 = csvjoin(2019)
df2020 = csvjoin(2020)

def dfparse(df):
# gives the row index of the row that contains 'Site Name' in the 'Day/Date' column
# as this changes between different years
idx = df.index[df['Day/Date'] == 'Site Name'].values[0]
dfcols = pd.DataFrame()
dfcols['rawcolname'] = df.columns
dfcols['sitename'] = df.iloc[idx,:].str.strip().values
dfcols['sitename'] = dfcols['sitename'].fillna('')
dfcols['cols'] = df.columns
dfcols['cols'] = dfcols.apply(lambda x: x['sitename'] + '_xx_' + x['cols'], axis=1)
colnamedict = dict(zip(dfcols['rawcolname'], dfcols['cols']))
Dictionary2 = {'Day/Date': 'Day/Date', 'Serial Date/Time': 'Serial Date/Time'}
colnamedict.update(Dictionary2)
df = df.rename(columns=colnamedict)

idx = df.index[df['Serial Date/Time'] == '1'].values[0]
df = df.iloc[idx,: ]
df = df.reset_index(drop=True)
df['Day/Date'] = df['Day/Date'].str.split().str[1]
df['Day/Date'] = pd.to_datetime(df['Day/Date'], format='%d/%m/%Y', UTC=True)
df['Serial Date/Time'] = df['Serial Date/Time'].astype('int64')
df['mod_serial'] = df['Serial Date/Time'].sub(1).mod(48).add(1)
# dfbig.loc[(dfbig['Day/Date'].isin(ClockForwardMarch)) & dfbig['mod_serial'].isin([2,
3])]
dropindex = df.loc[(df['Day/Date'].dt.strftime('%Y-%m-%d').isin(ClockForwardMarch)) &
df['mod_serial'].isin([3, 4])].index
df.drop(dropindex, inplace=True)
df = df.reset_index(drop=True)
# df=df2017
insert_row_number = df.loc[(df['Day/Date'].dt.strftime('%Y-%m-
%d').isin(ClockBackwardOctober))
& (df['mod_serial'] == 5)].index

# loop if the insert_row_number is not empty
if insert_row_number.size:
    insert_row_number = insert_row_number.item()
    # Slice the dataframe prior to the row insert
    df1 = df[0:insert_row_number]
    df1 = pd.concat([df1, pd.concat([df1[-1:]] * 2)])

    # Store the result of lower half of the dataframe
    df2 = df[insert_row_number:]
    # Concat the two dataframes
    df = pd.concat([df1, df2])

```

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```

df = df.reset_index(drop=True)
# tst = df['serial'].groupby(by=df['Day/Date']).count()
return df

df2017 = dfparse(df2017)
df2018 = dfparse(df2018)
df2019 = dfparse(df2019)
df2020 = dfparse(df2020)

dfbig = pd.concat([df2017, df2018, df2019, df2020])
dfbig = dfbig.reset_index(drop=True)
dfbig.insert(2, 'serial', dfbig.index)
startdatetime = dfbig['Day/Date'].iloc[0] - pd.Timedelta('1 hour')
enddatetime = dfbig['Day/Date'].iloc[-1] + pd.Timedelta('23 hours 30 minutes')
dfbig.insert(2, 'UTC', pd.date_range(start=startdatetime, end=enddatetime, freq='30 min',
tz='UTC'))
dfbig.insert(3, 'localtime', dfbig['UTC'].dt.tz_convert('Europe/London'))
coldrop = ['Day/Date', 'Serial Date/Time', 'serial', 'mod_serial']
dfbig = dfbig.drop(coldrop, axis=1)

os.chdir(folderpath)
datetimeserialcols = ['Day/Date', 'Serial Date/Time', 'UTC', 'localtime', 'serial',
'mod_serial']
lst = dfbig.columns[dfbig.columns.isin(datetimeserialcols) == False].str.split('_xx_')
lst2 = [item[0] for item in lst]
lst = np.unique(lst2)
NetworkCapMap['Primary Substation'].loc[NetworkCapMap['Primary Substation'].isin(lst)]
lstdf = pd.DataFrame()
lstdf['timeseries_primarynames'] = lst
primarycode_dict = dict(zip(NetworkCapMap['Primary Substation'], NetworkCapMap['Substation
Number']))
inv_primarycode_dict = dict(zip(NetworkCapMap['Substation Number'], NetworkCapMap['Substation
Name']))
lstdf['primarycodes_match_networkcapmap'] =
lstdf['timeseries_primarynames'].map(primarycode_dict)
lstdf['manual_networkcapmap_check'] = ''
# only needs to save to csv once or after a change, after this - its just reading in from the
copy
# lstdf.to_csv('manual_check_primary_names.csv', encoding='Utf-8', index=False)
lstcopy = pd.read_csv('manual_check_primary_names_copy.csv', skiprows=0, header=0,
encoding='Utf-8', dtype=str)
lstcopy['pcodes'] = np.where(lstcopy['primarycodes_match_networkcapmap'].isnull(),
lstcopy['manual_networkcapmap_check'],
lstcopy['primarycodes_match_networkcapmap'])

lstcopy['Substation Name'] = lstcopy['pcodes'].map(inv_primarycode_dict)
lstcopy['SubstationCodeName'] = lstcopy['pcodes'] + '_xx_' + lstcopy['Substation Name'] +
'_xxx_'
lstcopy['SubstationCodeName'] = np.where(lstcopy['SubstationCodeName'].isnull(),
'_xx_' + lstcopy['timeseries_primarynames'] + '_xxx_',
lstcopy['SubstationCodeName'])

# checked for any duplicates - none were found other than the nan
# lstcopy['pcodes'].duplicated(keep=False)
primarycodename_dict = dict(zip(lstcopy['timeseries_primarynames'],
lstcopy['SubstationCodeName']))
primarycode_dict = dict(zip(lstcopy['timeseries_primarynames'], lstcopy['pcodes']))
dfcols = pd.DataFrame()
dfcols['cols'] = dfbig.columns
dfcols['original'] = dfcols['cols'].str.split('_xx_').str[1]
dfcols['sitename'] = dfcols['cols'].str.split('_xx_').str[0]
dfcols['sitename_len'] = dfcols['sitename'].str.len().fillna(0).astype(int)
dfcols['mask'] = dfcols['cols'].str.contains('_xx_')
dfcols['Substation Number'] = dfcols['sitename'].map(primarycode_dict)
dfcols['Substation Number'] = dfcols['Substation Number'].replace(np.nan, '')
dfcols['Substation Number_len'] = dfcols['Substation Number'].str.len().fillna(0).astype(int)
dfcols['SubstationNumberName'] = dfcols['sitename'].map(primarycodename_dict)
dfcols['SubstationName'] =
dfcols['SubstationNumberName'].str.split('_xx_').str[1].str.split('_xxx_').str[0]

dfcols['tempcol'] = dfcols.apply(lambda x: x['cols'][(4+(x['sitename_len']*2)):], axis=1)

```

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```

# dfcols['tempcol'] = dfcols.apply(lambda x: x['original'][x['sitename_len':]], axis=1)
dfcols['newcol'] = dfcols['SubstationNumberName'] + dfcols['tempcol']
dfcols['newcolnames'] = np.where(dfcols['mask'] == True, dfcols['newcol'], dfcols['cols'])

coldict = dict(zip(dfcols['cols'], dfcols['newcolnames']))
dfbig = dfbig.rename(columns=coldict)

dropcols = ['cols', 'newcol']
dfcols = dfcols.drop(dropcols, axis=1)

dfdp = pd.read_csv('column_names_DP Additions2.csv', skiprows=0, header=0, encoding='Utf-8',
dtype=str)
feedercode_dict = dict(zip(dfdp['rawcolname'], dfdp['Feed']))
dfcols['feeder_number'] = dfcols['original'].map(feedercode_dict)
dfcols['pad'] = dfcols['feeder_number'].apply(lambda x: x.rjust(4, '0') if str(x).isnumeric()
else x)
dfcols['withcodes'] = (dfcols['Substation Number'] + '/' + dfcols['pad'] + '_xx_' +
dfcols['SubstationName'] + '_xxx_' + dfcols['tempcol'])
dfcols['withcodes'].loc[~dfcols['mask']] = dfcols['newcolnames'].loc[~dfcols['mask']]

coldict = dict(zip(dfcols['newcolnames'], dfcols['withcodes']))
dfbig = dfbig.rename(columns=coldict)

datetimelist = ['utc', 'localtime']
dfdatetime = dfbig[[col for col in dfbig.columns if col in datetimelist]]
dfnotdatetime = dfbig[[col for col in dfbig.columns if col not in datetimelist]]
dfnotdatetime = dfnotdatetime.apply(pd.to_numeric)
dfbig = pd.concat([dfdatetime, dfnotdatetime], axis=1)

lst = pd.DataFrame()
lst = dfcols.groupby(['SubstationName']).first().reset_index(drop=False)
lst['filenames'] = lst['SubstationName'].str.replace('/', '_')
# lst = pd.DataFrame(columns=['SubstationName', 'filenames'])
# lst['SubstationName'] = ['Dillotford Ave 33 11kv S Stn']
# lst['filenames'] = ['Dillotford Ave 33 11kv S Stn']

os.chdir(output_for_checking)
for i, x in enumerate(lst['SubstationName']):
    df = dfbig[datetimelist]
    collist = dfbig.columns[dfbig.columns.str.contains(x)].values
    for j, y in enumerate(collist):
        tempval1 = y.split('_xx_')[0]
        tempval2 = y.split('_xx_')[1]
        flagcolname = tempval1 + '_FLAG' + '_xx_' + tempval2
        colname = y
        # break

        df.loc[:, flagcolname] = np.where(dfbig[y].notnull(), 1, '')
        df.loc[:, colname] = dfbig[y]

# helpful snippet of code to check sum of true for regex search
# dfbig.columns.str.lower().str.strip().str.contains('t\d{1}power mva$').sum()

# regex search for columns that contain T then a digit then Power MVA at the end of the
string
# changed to lower for search and strip to reduce potential errors on trailing spaces or
# upper lower characters
# also search on columns that do not contain '_FLAG'
power_mva_cols = df.columns[
(df.columns.str.lower().str.strip().str.contains('t\d{1}power mva$')) &
(~df.columns.str.contains('_FLAG'))
]
power_mva = df.filter(power_mva_cols).sum(axis=1).mul(1000)

current_feeder_cols = df.columns[
(df.columns.str.contains('[/]\d{4}_')) &
(~df.columns.str.contains('_FLAG'))
]
current_feeder_sum = df.filter(current_feeder_cols).sum(axis=1).round(4)
power_from_current_feeder_sum_if11kv =
current_feeder_sum.mul(11).mul(math.sqrt(3)).round(4)
power_from_current_feeder_sum_if6dot6kv =

```

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```
current_feeder_sum.mul(6.6).mul(math.sqrt(3)).round(4)

    colname = tempvall.split('/')[0] + '_xx_' + x + '_xxx_# str(x)
    df.insert(2, f'{colname}kw_from_current_feeder_sum_if6dot6kv',
power_from_current_feeder_sum_if6dot6kv, allow_duplicates=False)
    df.insert(2, f'{colname}kw_from_current_feeder_sum_if11kv',
power_from_current_feeder_sum_if11kv, allow_duplicates=False)
    df.insert(2, f'{colname}amps_current_feeder_sum', current_feeder_sum,
allow_duplicates=False)

    filename = lst.loc[i, 'filenames']
    # list(dfbig).to_csv('column_names.csv', encoding='Utf-8', index=False)
    df.to_csv(f'RESO_WPD_{filename.upper()}_WITHFLAGCOLS.csv', encoding='Utf-8', index=False)

lst.to_csv('RESO_WPD_for_primary_codes.csv', encoding='Utf-8', index=False)
# dfcols.to_csv('RESO_WPD_for_feeder_codes.csv', encoding='Utf-8', index=True)
# dfbig.to_csv('RESO_WPD_CSV_v01_All_PrimaryMonitoring_2017_2020rawraw.csv', encoding='Utf-8',
index=True)
print("time elapsed: {:.2f}s".format(time.time() - start_time))
```

APPENDIX 5 - WORKFLOW TAKEN TO ACCESS MONITORING DATA FROM WPD

WPD Monitoring data for RESO was accessed and transferred using the following steps:

- 1) **Implement good data sharing practice:** RESO ensured proper data management and controls¹¹ for handling all 3rd Party shared/volume data.
- 2) **Initial Sweep list** - all Primary substations of interest were used as an initial sweep selection list (Figure 5). This was found to be good for area coverage at *Primary* level but later found to miss out useful data at higher network-levels. See below for BSP/GSP improvements)
- 3) Find corresponding **input names** - sweep list was used to find the correct input names for the extract query:
 - a. Request a sample of all-sites monitoring data (short time span, small file)
 - b. Match known site names of interest – capture each input name
 - c. Assemble list of all required sites for re-input to get the full extract (large file).

The 28 input site names initially used are detailed in Figure 5. After lengthy inspection of full data, it was discovered that a more complete data set would need 5 further sites (above primary) to cover all BSP and GSP sites.

- 4) **Run full query** – executed with the help of the WPD Innovation Team
- 5) **Check all required network assets** were captured (RESO later found more of interest) – log any missing for subsequent query as required, where more data is available. The coverage of all key assets over all times/years of interest–transformers and major cable routes was checked. Some project calculations

¹¹ Good data management within RESO are built upon:

- o the RESO Consortium Agreement;
- o data sharing principles and systems provided by Energy Systems Catapult;
- o the ERIS data portal provided via ESC (esdc.org) includes access controls and audit trails together with functions to add user agreement(s) to support and protect both data owners and users and to control the proper usage of data.

of power in an area were tested, these may hinge on the completeness and coverage of this one-time data extract.

- 6) **Batches of data were obtained** in sizes that could be transferred readily from WPD to a 3rd Party (as is normal in many secure business operations, corporate network access and large file copying is security restricted). Issues with this are noted below.

For RESO wider team use, data was transferred to the ESC data portal where the project use is under the restrictive data management control "Private Access for RESO team". Data was loaded raw, with no parsing of data attempted post-query.

Limits to data access: WPD key operational systems and data – including monitoring - are all duly secured and protected by a number of internal security measures (more restrictive than for systems designed to be open: private connections and secure query tools must be used and WPD resources are needed to access/query data). Until integrated and common information models are implemented and more systematic dissemination explored by DNOs, to minimise waste and costs DNOs will welcome moderation in how often this interim query data is requested. This is due to the manual sequential steps in query and export and to keep each set of data consistent with others. Access to DNO systems may also be delayed during times of operational priority (such as the recent Coronavirus lockdown when access to corporate networks and IT systems can also be limited).

APPENDIX 6 – LIST OF DATA IN NETWORK CAPACITY MAP

Network Reference ID
Parent Network Reference ID
Substation Name
Substation Number
Asset Type
Latitude
Longitude
Fault Level Headroom
Group
Bulk Supply Point Name
Primary Substation
Upstream Voltage
Downstream Voltage
Firm Capacity of Substation (MVA)
Reverse Power Capability (MVA)
Measured Peak Demand (MVA)
Upstream Equipment Ratings 3Ph Make (kA)

Upstream Equipment Ratings 3Ph Break (kA)
Upstream Short Circuit Currents 3Ph Make (kA)
Upstream Short Circuit Currents 3Ph Break (kA)
Downstream Equipment Ratings 3Ph Make (kA)
Downstream Equipment Ratings 3Ph Break (kA)
Downstream Short Circuit Currents 3Ph Make (kA)
Downstream Short Circuit Currents 3Ph Break (kA)
Upstream Equipment Ratings 1Ph Make (kA)
Upstream Equipment Ratings 1Ph Break (kA)
Upstream Short Circuit Currents 1Ph Make (kA)
Upstream Short Circuit Currents 1Ph Break (kA)
Downstream Equipment Ratings 1Ph Make (kA)
Downstream Equipment Ratings 1Ph Break (kA)
Downstream Short Circuit Currents 1Ph Make (kA)
Downstream Short Circuit Currents 1Ph Break (kA)
Demand Headroom (MVA)
Generation Headroom (MVA)
Fault Level Headroom (kA)
Total Inferred Generation (MVA)
Demand Headroom RAG
Generation Headroom RAG
Fault Level Headroom RAG
Aggregated Demand Headroom RAG
Aggregated Generation Headroom RAG
Upstream Demand Headroom RAG
Upstream Generation Headroom RAG
Generator Types
Generation Connected (kVA)
Generation Offered Not Accepted (kVA)
Generation Accepted Not Connected (kVA)
Statement of Work [1] Date From
Statement of Work [1] Date To
Statement of Work [1] Text
Statement of Work [1] URL
Statement of Work [2] Date From
Statement of Work [2] Date To
Statement of Work [2] Text
Statement of Work [2] URL
Statement of Work [3] Date From
Statement of Work [3] Date To
Statement of Work [3] Text

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Statement of Work [3] URL
Statement of Work [4] Date From
Statement of Work [4] Date To
Statement of Work [4] Text
Statement of Work [4] URL
Statement of Work [5] Date From
Statement of Work [5] Date To
Statement of Work [5] Text
Statement of Work [5] URL

